

Coralysis enables sensitive identification of imbalanced cell types and states in single-cell data via multi-level integration

António G.G. Sousa^{*1,✉}, Johannes Smolander^{†1}, Sini Junttila^{‡1}, and Laura L. Elo^{§1,2,✉}

¹Turku Bioscience Centre, University of Turku and Abo Akademi University,

Tykistökatu 6, 20520 Turku, Finland

²Institute of Biomedicine, University of Turku, 20520 Turku, Finland

✉To whom correspondence should be addressed: António G.G. Sousa

(aggode@utu.fi) & Laura L. Elo (laura.elo@utu.fi)

*aggode@utu.fi

†johannes.smolander@helsinki.fi

‡simaju@utu.fi

§laura.elo@utu.fi

Abstract

Current state-of-the-art integration methods for single-cell transcriptomics often struggle with imbalanced cell types across heterogeneous datasets, particularly when the datasets include similar but unshared cell types. Here, we introduce Coralysis, an R package featuring a multi-level integration algorithm to overcome these challenges. Coralysis enables sensitive integration, reference-mapping, and cell state identification across single-cell datasets, demonstrating consistent performance across diverse single-cell RNA-seq integration tasks and outperforming state-of-the-art methods when similar cell types are unevenly distributed across batches or completely absent from some datasets. Beyond single-cell transcriptomics, Coralysis enables the integration of rare cell populations from single-cell proteomic assays, such as basophils (0.5%) from whole blood. It also accurately predicts cell type identities across various query-reference scenarios. For instance, it successfully reclassifies CD16+ monocytes and natural killer cells that were previously misclassified as CD14+ monocytes and cytotoxic T cells in peripheral blood mononuclear cells. Finally, a key feature of Coralysis is its ability to provide probability scores that enable identifying both transient and steady cell states along with their differential expression programs. Overall, Coralysis facilitates the study of subtle biological variation and its dynamics by improving the integration of imbalanced cell types and states, enabling a more faithful representation of the cellular landscape in complex single-cell experiments.

1 1 Introduction

2 Single-cell transcriptomes from multiple subjects across different biological conditions
3 can provide valuable insights into varying biological phenomena, such as cell trajecto-
4 ries¹ in embryonic development or differential gene expression² between healthy and
5 diseased individuals. In analysing such datasets, a typical goal is to project and clus-
6 ter the multi-subject single-cell transcriptomes into a low-dimensional space, ensuring
7 that cells of the same type cluster together. However, technical noise introduced due
8 to handling sets of samples distinctively, i.e., in batches, can distort the biological sig-
9 nal, leading to an unwanted outcome, where cells are clustered based on their batch
10 identity rather than cell type. Correcting for such technical batch effect biases by inte-
11 grating and “aligning” cells across batches is crucial to preserve the biological signal
12 and accurately clustering the same cell types together.

13 A few benchmarks have been conducted so far to evaluate horizontal integration meth-
14 ods for single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq)^{3–5}. They differ on the type of data
15 used, the complexity of the integration tasks tested, and the performance metrics cal-
16 culated. Tran *et al.*³ compared fourteen integration methods across five different inte-
17 gration tasks varying in complexity using four assessment metrics. They recommended
18 Harmony⁶, LIGER⁷, and Seurat v3⁸ methods based on their overall performance. On
19 the other hand, Richards *et al.*⁴ focused on assessing batch correction specifically
20 for cancer scRNA-seq data integration using the LISI (Local Inverse Simpson’s Index)
21 metric. Among the five tools tested, STACAS⁹ and fastMNN¹⁰ were identified as the
22 most adequate methods regarding their ability to batch-correct the data but still re-

23 tain tumour-specific biological variability. A more recent benchmark by Luecken *et*
24 *al.*⁵ used the most comprehensive set of integration performance metrics to date to
25 compare sixteen integration methods across seven scRNA-seq datasets with/without
26 scaling and with/without feature selection. The overall three top-performing methods
27 were scANVI¹¹, Scanorama¹² and scVI¹³. The lack of agreement between these inde-
28 pendent benchmarks reflects that there is no single method fitting all the integration
29 tasks. Instead, the choice of the most suitable method depends greatly on the aim of
30 the study, the type of data, and the degree of noise introduced by the batch.

31 Among these methods, scANVI and scVI tools are deep neural network methods that
32 are very effective in correcting complex batch effects,⁵ though they are less inter-
33 pretable. In addition, scANVI requires cell label annotations, which are quite often
34 absent, whereas scVI performs better with larger numbers of cells and more complex
35 batch correction tasks⁵. In contrast, Scanorama, fastMNN, Seurat v3, and STACAS in-
36 tegrate the data through mutual nearest neighbours searches in a joint low-dimensional
37 embedding, which provides the ability to remove technical noise at lower computa-
38 tional cost^{5,14}. However, the use of a joint low-dimensional representation to integrate
39 the batches may cause cell type “misalignment” in case there is a lack of cell type
40 conservation across batches^{3,14}. LIGER uses integrative non-negative matrix factor-
41 ization to identify shared factors across batches,⁷ whereas Harmony is a linear integra-
42 tion method that applies iteratively K -means clustering in principal component space⁶.
43 Both tend to prioritise batch correction over biological conservation,⁵ making them less
44 suitable to integrate datasets with nuanced biological cell states.

45 Here, we introduce Coralys, an R package featuring a multi-level integration algorithm
46 for sensitive integration, reference-mapping, and cell state identification in single-cell
47 data. Coralys performs consistently well across diverse scRNA-seq integration tasks
48 and query-reference scenarios. It outperforms state-of-the-art integration methods in
49 tasks where batches do not share similar cell types, enables integration of rare cell
50 populations beyond transcriptomics, including single-cell proteomic assays, as well as
51 accurate reference-mapping of previously misclassified cells. Finally, a key feature of
52 Coralys is that it provides probability scores to identify transient and steady cell states
53 along with their differential expression programs, providing a comprehensive approach
54 for single-cell data integration.

55 **2 Methods**

56 **2.1 Iterative Clustering Projection algorithm: adaptations**

57 A multi-level integration method was implemented in Coralys by adapting the Itera-
58 tive Clustering Projection (ICP) algorithm, available in ILoReg,¹⁵ to work in a top-down
59 fashion. In addition, clustering accuracy was improved and biases towards more abun-
60 dant cell types and batches were effectively corrected. Coralys is distributed as an
61 R package and it is available at <https://github.com/elolab/Coralys>. The ICP
62 algorithm is described briefly in the next paragraph as it is at the core of our method.
63 ICP relies mainly on two consecutive steps performed at every epoch of each of the L
64 ICP runs ($L = 200$ by default): (1) logistic regression with $L1$ regularization to predict
65 cluster probabilities; and (2) *Adjusted Rand Index* (aka *ARI*) to compare the similarity

66 between cluster assignments across epochs. Step 1 aims to predict clusters using the
67 ability of $L1$ -regularized logistic regression to learn from the data important features
68 and translate that into a probability matrix, $N \times K$, with the likelihood of every N cell
69 belonging to each one of the K clusters ($K = 15$ by default). In order to predict cluster
70 probabilities, step 1 starts by using a balanced random initial clustering S where one of
71 the K clusters is assigned to each N cell with equal probability. The training data set
72 is created by downsampling each cell cluster to an equal number of cells. The down-
73 sampling depends on parameter d (0.3 by default), meaning that 30% of the cells from
74 each cluster are selected. An $L1$ -regularized logistic regression classifier is trained on
75 the trained data and used to classify the whole data, resulting in a new projected clus-
76 tering S' . Then, step 2 compares the ARI score between the clusterings S and S' . If
77 $ARI(S', S)$ increases from its previous value (initialized to zero in the first epoch), the
78 new clustering S' is used to perform the next epoch, i.e., step 1, otherwise S is used to
79 repeat step 1 until the maximum number of reiterations r is reached ($r = 5$ by default).
80 Alternatively, the ARI score can increase consecutively until the maximum number of
81 iterations $max.iter$ is reached ($max.iter = 200$). Step 2 works as a measure to direct
82 predictions towards more stable clusters and to improve the ability of the regularized
83 regression to learn from the data. Once the best ARI value is reached for a given
84 ICP run, i.e., the best clustering result, the algorithm jumps to the next ICP round until
85 $L = 200$.
86 The adaptations introduced to the ICP algorithm will be described in the sections below.

87 **2.1.1 Training set**

88 In order to overcome the need for using the same data for training and testing, as it was
89 originally implemented, Coralysis builds a separate training set from the data. The pro-
90 cess involves four steps: (1) selecting highly variable genes (HVGs) (by default 2,000)
91 with the `scrn` R package¹⁶; (2) performing a principal component analysis (PCA) us-
92 ing the HVGs (default PCs=30) with the `irlba` package¹⁷; (3) using the selected PCs
93 to cluster cells into a large number of clusters (by default 500) with *k*-means++ from
94 the package `flexclust`¹⁸; and (4) averaging gene expression within the clusters found at
95 step (3). This results in a training set that is more balanced, less sparse and distinct
96 from the testing data avoiding overfitting and improving the overall accuracy of classifi-
97 cation, particularly, due to the reduced bias towards abundant cell types and batches.
98 In addition, the ICP algorithm converges faster and uses less memory due to reduced
99 dimensionality. In the presence of a known batch, this process is applied batch wise
100 and the resulting datasets are concatenated into a joint training set.

101 **2.1.2 Number of clusters at start: 2**

102 A cluster seed approach was implemented to assign every cell to one of the two clus-
103 ters required at the start of the divisive ICP algorithm. The approach consists of assign-
104 ing cells, in a batch wise manner, to one of the two clusters based on their distribution
105 along the first principal component. A PCA is performed with the `irlba` package on the
106 standardized data (Z-score) comprising all the cells, regardless of the batch, and all
107 genes with a non-zero standard deviation. Then, the cells with a batch wise PC1 score

108 lower than or equal to the median batch wise PC1 score are assigned to cluster number
109 one and the other cells to cluster number two. The same cluster seed is given across
110 the multiple ICP runs. This approach reduces the algorithm runtime, as it takes less
111 epochs to converge, and it favours integration due to the more concordant clusterings
112 obtained across multiple ICP runs. The aim of the cluster seed approach is to provide
113 a rough, meaningful clustering result that is not robust, allowing the ICP algorithm to
114 iterate over the clusters and converge. If a training set is built from the original data,
115 the cluster seed process is performed over clusters of cells rather than cells.

116 **2.1.3 Cells for training: batch k -NN**

117 At every epoch, except the first, the cell with the highest probability for each batch
118 within each cluster is identified based on the current clustering and the associated
119 probabilities. The respective k -nearest neighbors (k -NN) are then selected for training
120 the $L1$ -regularized logistic regression model with the RANN package¹⁹. The number of
121 neighbours k can be specified as fixed or proportional to the cluster size. By default, k
122 is set to 30% of the cells (or cell clusters) comprising the cluster divided by the number
123 of batches. This selection procedure aims to find the most similar cells across batches
124 by using probability as a proxy for similarity and to achieve a more balanced set of cells
125 for training. Additionally, it contributes to the faster convergence of the ICP algorithm
126 by relying on the neighbours of the cells with the highest probabilities. If a training set
127 is used, the selection procedure of cells for training is performed over clusters of cells
128 rather than cells.

129 **2.1.4 Divisive clustering:** $2 \rightarrow 4$

130 The ICP algorithm¹⁵ was adapted to perform clustering in a top-down fashion by se-
131 quentially increasing the number of clusters in powers of two, i.e., 2^k , where $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$,
132 until it reaches the target number of clusters (by default 16) - also in the power of
133 two. The divisive clustering process begins with two clusters assigned by the cluster
134 seed procedure described in section 2.1.2. ICP iterates over these two clusters until
135 convergence. This process results in the assignment of a cluster label (1 or 2) and a
136 probability score to every cell. The probability score indicates the likelihood of a cell
137 belonging to one cluster and not the other. Next, each cluster is divided into two based
138 on their cluster probability distribution (median as default cutoff) in a batch wise manner
139 to avoid bias. Then ICP iterates over the four clusters until convergence. This incre-
140 mental clustering process is repeated until the target number of clusters is reached (by
141 default 16: $2 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 16$). If a training set is used, the divisive clustering process is
142 applied over clusters of cells rather than cells.

143 **2.2 Coralysis reference-mapping method**

144 The Coralysis reference-mapping method relies solely on the ICP algorithm. This
145 means that an annotated reference trained with the divisive or the original ICP algo-
146 rithm can be used to classify and project new unannotated query single-cell datasets.
147 First, an annotated reference, i.e., with known cell types, is trained with ICP and the
148 resulting cluster probabilities are used to perform PCA with the *stats* package²⁰. Sec-
149 ond, the cluster probabilities and PCA scores are predicted for the query or unanno-

150 tated dataset(s). This procedure is dataset-independent, as cluster probabilities and
151 PCA scores are predicted cell wise. Third, a k -NN classifier, from the package *class*²¹,
152 is trained with the reference PCA and labels to transfer. Finally, the built k -NN model
153 is used to classify the query cells using k neighbours (by default 10) and the winning
154 class is decided by majority voting. The proportion of k nearest neighbours for the
155 winning class is used as an indication of confidence. Additionally, the query PCA data
156 can be projected onto the reference Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
157 (UMAP).

158 **2.3 Benchmarking integration: scib-pipeline**

159 Coralysis integration method was benchmarked against six unsupervised integration
160 methods (scVI, Scanorama, Seurat v4 CCA/RPCA, Harmony, fastMNN) across six
161 datasets (pancreas, lung, human immune, human/mouse immune, two simulations)
162 using 14 assessment metrics within the publicly available scib-pipeline ([https://github](https://github.com/theislab/scib-pipeline)
163 [ub.com/theislab/scib-pipeline](https://github.com/theislab/scib-pipeline))⁵. The mouse brain dataset was not included in the
164 benchmark because it was not available on figshare with the other datasets due to size
165 limitations. A detailed description of the datasets can be found in Luecken *et al.*⁵. The
166 version of R and Seurat was updated to 4.1.3 and 4.3, respectively. The forked version
167 of the *theislab/scib-pipeline* github repository with the adaptations required to repro-
168 duce the benchmark is available at: <https://github.com/elolab/scib-pipeline>.
169 The benchmark was run with Snakemake (v.7.25.2) in a cluster environment with Slurm
170 (v.23.02.6) with 8 threads and 354 GB of RAM.

171 **2.4 Accuracy of reference-mapping across query-reference sce-** 172 **narios**

173 The accuracy of Coralysis reference-mapping method was assessed across four dif-
174 ferent query-reference scenarios: 1) imbalanced cell types; 2) unshared cell types; 3)
175 unrepresented batch; and 4) a varied strength of the batch effect. Performance was
176 measured in terms of accuracy as follows:

$$177 \text{ Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN},$$

178 with TP = True Positives, TN = True Negatives, FP = False Positives, FN = False
179 Negatives. These analyses were performed with the R programming language in a
180 containerized docker image publicly available at Docker Hub (elolabfi/sctoolkit) running
181 R (v.4.2.1)²⁰ (<https://www.r-project.org/>) and RStudio server (2022.07.2 Build 576).

182 **2.4.1 Imbalanced cell types**

183 Two scRNA-seq datasets (batch 1 and 2) of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs)
184 were used to assess the accuracy of reference-mapping for a scenario when the refer-
185 ence has imbalanced cell types relative to the query. The batch 1 dataset was used as
186 reference and the batch 2 as query. Each dataset was comprised of six balanced cell
187 types (B cell, CD4 T cell, CD8 T cell, Monocyte_CD14, Monocyte_FCGR3A, NK cell),
188 i.e., each cell type had the same number of cells ($n=200$). In total, each dataset had
189 1,200 cells and 33,694 genes. The analyzed PBMC datasets are from Maan *et al.*²²
190 and they can be downloaded at figshare: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24>

191 625302.v1. Both datasets were normalised by applying the natural-log transformation
192 to the gene expression counts, divided by the total counts per cell multiplied by a scal-
193 ing factor (10,000). The reference-mapping was performed by randomly downsampling
194 one cell type in the reference to 10%; training the reference with ICP (2,000 HVGs);
195 and projecting and classifying the query against the reference. This procedure was
196 repeated independently for every cell type in the reference.

197 **2.4.2 Unshared cell types**

198 The two PBMC datasets used for the imbalanced cell type query-reference scenario
199 were used for assessing the performance of the reference-mapping when the reference
200 has unshared cell types relative to the query. The reference-mapping analysis followed
201 the same procedure described in section 2.4.1 but replacing the downsampling by
202 ablation, i.e., completely removing one cell type at a time from the reference.

203 **2.4.3 Unrepresented batch**

204 A set of pancreatic scRNA-seq datasets comprising eight samples (celseq, celseq2,
205 smartseq2, fluidigm1, indrop1, indrop2, indrop3, indrop4) sequenced across five li-
206 brary preparation technologies (SMARTSeq2, Fluidigm C1, CelSeq, CelSeq2, inDrops)
207 was used to assess the performance of reference-mapping with and without shared
208 batch effects. Every sample corresponded to a pancreatic scRNA-seq dataset se-
209 quenced using a different library preparation technology with the exception of the sam-
210 ples indrop1, indrop2, indrop3, indrop4 which corresponded to four biological replicates
211 coming from the same technology inDrops. The datasets were normalised as de-

212 scribed in section 2.4.1 and genes not expressed were removed. In total, the datasets
213 comprised 14,890 cells and 29,340 expressed genes. The number of cells per sam-
214 ple varied from 638 in fluidigmc1 to 3,605 in indrop3 (celseq=1,004; indrop4=1,303;
215 indrop2=1,724; indrop1=1,937; celseq2=2,285; smartseq2=2,394). A reference was
216 built by integrating six samples - celseq, celseq2, fluidigmc1, indrop1, indrop3, indrop4
217 - using Coralysis with 2,000 highly variable genes. The samples indrop2 and smart-
218 seq2 were chosen as query datasets representing a scenario of a shared and unshared
219 batch effect between the reference-query, respectively. Then the query datasets were
220 classified and projected onto the integrated reference with Coralysis. The pancreatic
221 datasets used herein were obtained from the SeuratData package (v.0.2.1).

222 **2.4.4 A varied strength of the batch effect**

223 Two human PBMC scRNA-seq samples representing resting and interferon-stimulated
224 cells were used for assessing the performance of reference-mapping when the gene
225 expression of different cell types within a sample respond distinctly to a batch effect or
226 a biological condition, i.e., the transcriptome changes more for some cell types than
227 others. The resting sample was chosen as reference (6,548 cells) and the interferon-
228 stimulated sample as query (7,451). The datasets were normalised as described in
229 section 2.4.1 and genes not expressed were removed. In total, the samples comprised
230 14,044 genes and 13,999 cells. The reference was trained using Coralysis with 2,000
231 highly variable genes and the query classified and projected onto the reference. The
232 PBMC data used for this task was obtained from the SeuratData package (v.0.2.1).

233 2.5 Integration of PBMCs from two 10X 3' assays

234 Two 10X scRNA-seq 3' assays - V1 and V2 - from human peripheral blood mononuclear
235 cells (PBMCs) were integrated with Coralysis to demonstrate multi-level integration in
236 practice. Both assays were downloaded from the 10X website: V1 ([https://supp](https://support.10xgenomics.com/single-cell-gene-expression/datasets/1.1.0/pbmc6k)
237 [ort.10xgenomics.com/single-cell-gene-expression/datasets/1.1.0/pbmc6k](https://support.10xgenomics.com/single-cell-gene-expression/datasets/1.1.0/pbmc6k))
238 and V2 ([https://support.10xgenomics.com/single-cell-gene-expression/da](https://support.10xgenomics.com/single-cell-gene-expression/datasets/2.1.0/pbmc8k)
239 [tasetes/2.1.0/pbmc8k](https://support.10xgenomics.com/single-cell-gene-expression/datasets/2.1.0/pbmc8k)). Cells were annotated using the annotations provided by Ko-
240 rsunsky *et al.* - Source Data Figure 4 file⁶. Cells without annotation were discarded
241 (143 cells). Duplicated gene symbols were renamed by appending the correspond-
242 ing Ensembl IDs. Genes not expressed were removed. In total 20,016 genes and
243 13,016 cells remained - 4,770 cells in V1 and 8,276 cells in V2. Normalisation was
244 done similarly as in section 2.4.1. Highly variable genes (HVG=2,000) were selected
245 with the package *scrn*. The two assays were integrated using Coralysis by running
246 the function *RunParallelDivisiveICP*, using 2,000 HVGs and default parameters, ex-
247 cept for *allow.free.k = FALSE*, *C = 1*, *train.k.nn.prop = 0.45*, and *ari.cutoff = 0.1*,
248 which were specified to ensure that Coralysis returned exactly 16 clusters. By default,
249 *allow.free.k = TRUE*, allowing clusters without assigned cells to be dropped among
250 the target number of clusters (default 16). Setting *allow.free.k = FALSE* overrides
251 this behavior to enforce the return of all 16 clusters with the support of more relaxed
252 parameters: *C = 1*, *train.k.nn.prop = 0.45*, and *ari.cutoff = 0.1*. The probability
253 tables for each final divisive round at *K=2*, *K=4*, *K=8*, and *K=16* were independently
254 concatenated across the 50 ICP runs to compute a PCA and *t*-SNE with Coralysis.

255 Probabilities were centered and scaled before PCA. The divisive ICP clustering run
256 number two ($L=2$) corresponding to the cluster probability table (at $K16$) with the high-
257 est standard deviation was selected to exemplify the evolution of batch label mixing
258 and cell type separation across one divisive ICP run (the algorithm was run 50 times).
259 The top ten positive coefficients for every cluster across the four divisive ICP rounds
260 for the run number 2 were also retrieved. The t -SNE and cluster tree plots were made
261 with ggplot2 (v.3.5.1)²³, pie charts with scatterpie (v.0.2.3)²⁴ and heatmaps with Com-
262 plexHeatmap (v.2.14.0)²⁵.

263 **2.6 Integrating similar unshared cell type pairs**

264 Two PBMC scRNA-seq samples, one representing resting PBMCs (CTRL) and other
265 PBCMs stimulated with interferon (STIM), were used to highlight the ability of Coralys
266 to integrate similar unshared cell type pairs across batches. The *ifnb* dataset (v.3.1.0)
267 published by Kang *et al.*²⁶ was obtained from the SeuratData R package (v.0.2.1). Cells
268 were normalized as described in section 2.4.1 and genes not expressed were removed.
269 Two pairs of similar cell types that responded differently to interferon stimulation were
270 selected: CD14–CD16 monocytes and CD4 naive–memory T cells. Monocytes re-
271 sponded more strongly to the stimulation than T cells, making them easier to integrate
272 in this scenario. For each selected cell type pair, one cell type was retained in one
273 sample and removed from the other to simulate a situation where batches do not share
274 similar cell types. Specifically, CD16 monocytes (507 cells) and CD4 memory T cells
275 (859) were retained in the CTRL sample but removed from STIM, while CD14 mono-

276 cytes (2,147) and CD4 naive T cells (1,526) were retained in STIM but removed from
277 CTRL. In total 14,044 genes and 9,366 cells remained (3,355 cells in CTRL and 6,011
278 in STIM). Finally, the integration task was run through the scib-pipeline as described
279 in section 2.3. The *stim* and *seurat_annotatations* cell metadata columns were used as
280 batch and cell type labels, respectively.

281 **2.7 Integration of single-cell proteomics assays**

282 Two types of single-cell proteomics assays were integrated with Coralysis: antibody
283 derived tags (ADT) and cytometry by time of flight (CyTOF). The datasets were ob-
284 tained from <https://github.com/single-cell-proteomic/SCPRO-HI>²⁷. The cell
285 type annotations used were the same as given in Koca & Sevilgen²⁷. The ADT data
286 consisted of human PBMCs from eight HIV-infected donors (P1-8) following their lon-
287 gitudinal response across vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals (published by Hao
288 *et al.*²⁸). Batch 1 comprised donors P1-4, and batch 2 donors P5-8. In total, the ADT
289 dataset included 228 proteins and 161,764 cells (67,090 and 94,674 cells in batch 1
290 and 2, respectively). Cells were transformed using centered log-ratio (CLR) normaliza-
291 tion prior to integration, utilizing the *NormalizeData* function from Seurat. The batch
292 and cell type labels used were *Batch* and *cluster_s*, respectively. The *celltype.l2* labels
293 originally given in Hao *et al.*²⁸ were also highlighted.

294 The CyTOF data consisted of human whole blood datasets from Rahil *et al.*²⁹ and
295 Bjornson-Hooper *et al.*³⁰. The dataset from Rahil *et al.*²⁹ included whole blood from
296 35 donors infected with H1N1 influenza across 11 time points, while the dataset from

297 Bjornson-Hooper *et al.*³⁰ comprised blood samples from healthy donors exposed *in*
298 *vitro* to 15 different stimuli. Only the data corresponding to the IFN γ stimulus was used
299 for the latter. The dataset integrated included the expression of 39 proteins across
300 216,322 cells (102,147 cells from *h1n1* dataset, and 114,175 cells from *ifng* dataset).
301 The two datasets were considered as batches and the *cluster_s* cell metadata column
302 as the cell type label. The dataset was scaled (Z-score) by proteins before integration.
303 The first seven principal components were used for building the training set instead of
304 the default 30 due to the low number of features ($n=39$).
305 In both integration tasks, all features were used for integration and the resulting prob-
306 abilities were centered and scaled before PCA with Coralysis. In addition, the fast
307 implemented version of UMAP available in the uwot (v.0.1.14)³¹ R package was used
308 to compute UMAP. The python package scib-metrics⁵ was used to compute batch-
309 correction and bio-conservation metrics without the calculation of isolated labels as
310 the batches shared all cell types.

311 **2.8 Mapping PBMCs from different sequencing technologies**

312 The *pbmcsca* scRNA-seq dataset (v.3.0.0) from SeuratData was used to quantify the
313 mapping accuracy performance of Coralysis. The dataset published by Ding *et al.*³²
314 comprised nine PBMC samples prepared with different single-cell library preparation
315 technologies: 10x Chromium (v2) A, 10x Chromium (v2), 10x Chromium (v2) B, 10x
316 Chromium (v3), CEL-Seq2, Drop-seq, inDrops, Seq-Well, Smart-seq2. The sample
317 corresponding to PBMCs obtained through 10x Chromium (v2) A (3,222 cells) was

318 selected as a reference and the remaining as query datasets (27,753 cells). Cells
319 without annotation, i.e., with label *Unassigned* in *CellType* cell metadata column, were
320 removed. The data were normalised as described in section 2.4.1 and genes not ex-
321 pressed were discarded. The top 2,000 most highly variable genes were selected with
322 the scran function *modelGeneVar* for the reference sample (10x Chromium (v2) A). The
323 reference sample was trained with Coralys function *RunParallelDivisiveICP*, with
324 default parameters, with the exception of *divisive.method = "cluster"*, as the reference
325 sample did not have cells originating from different batches, i.e., *batch.label = NULL*.
326 The PCA and UMAP were computed with Coralys with the argument *return.model =*
327 *TRUE*. Probabilities were scaled prior to PCA as described in section 2.5. Reference-
328 mapping was computed with Coralys function *ReferenceMapping* with default pa-
329 rameters and cells were projected onto the reference UMAP (*project.umap = TRUE*).
330 Visualizations were obtained with Coralys, ggplot2 (v.3.5.1), and scater (v.1.26.1)³³.

331 **2.9 Inference of cell states with cell cluster probabilities**

332 CD34+ hematopoietic stem cells from Persad *et al.*³⁴ were used to show how Coral-
333 ysis cell cluster probability can be biologically meaningful. The scRNA-seq dataset
334 consisted of 6,881 cells downloaded from Zenodo: [https://zenodo.org/records](https://zenodo.org/records/6383269/files/cd34_multiome_rna.h5ad)
335 [/6383269/files/cd34_multiome_rna.h5ad](https://zenodo.org/records/6383269/files/cd34_multiome_rna.h5ad). The top 2,000 highly variable genes
336 were selected with the scran function *getTopHVGs* before running Coralys function
337 *RunParallelDivisiveICP* with *divisive.method = "cluster"*. UMAP was calculated
338 with the uwot package and parameters were adjusted to provide more connectivity:

339 $n_neighbors = 100$, $min_dist = 0.5$. The *palantir_pseudotime*³⁵ variable was used to
340 compute the Pearson correlation with the mean cell cluster probability obtained with
341 Coralysis across 50 ICP runs. The cell type labels used corresponded to those avail-
342 able in the *celltype* variable as used in the original study.
343 Human embryoid body cells (31,029 cells) from Moon *et al.*³⁶ were integrated by em-
344 bryonic stage (0-1, 2-3, 4-5, 6-7, 8-9) with Coralysis using 6,000 HVGs. UMAP was
345 computed as described above for the CD34+ cells dataset. The Coralysis cell cluster
346 probabilities were divided into 20 evenly sized bins for each cell type independently.
347 Gene expression and cell cluster probabilities were then averaged within each bin for
348 each cell type to calculate the Pearson correlation between them.
349 Visualisations were obtained with ggplot2 (v.3.5.1) and ComplexHeatmap (v.2.14.0).

350 **2.10 Data availability**

351 All datasets analysed in this study have been previously published and made publicly
352 available by the original authors. Links to each dataset are provided in the methods
353 section alongside their descriptions.

354 **2.11 Code availability**

355 The multi-level integration and reference-mapping methods have been implemented
356 into the R package Coralysis publicly available on GitHub: <https://github.com/elolab/Coralysis>. The forked version of the *theislabs/scib - pipeline* github repository with
357 the adaptations required to reproduce the benchmark described herein is available at:
358

359 <https://github.com/elolab/scib-pipeline>. Finally, all the R and python scripts
360 required to reproduce the remaining analyses and figures are available at: <https://github.com/elolab/Coralysis-reproducibility>.

362 **3 Results**

363 **3.1 Coralysis identifies cell types through multi-level integration**

364 Coralysis identifies shared cell subpopulations (cell types or states) across a given set
365 of heterogeneous single-cell datasets through four main steps (see Extended Data Fig.
366 1A). The first step clusters the cells batch-wise in a low dimensional space (PCA) using
367 Kmeans++¹⁸ with a large number of clusters (default 500). These clusters are used to
368 average the feature expression in order to build a training set. The second step uses
369 the built training set to identify shared cell clusters across datasets through divisive ICP
370 modelling. In the third step, the cluster probability is predicted for every cell against ev-
371 ery ICP model. Finally, the fourth step concatenates the cluster probability matrices
372 and performs a PCA to determine an integrated embedding, which can be used for
373 downstream clustering or non-linear dimensionality reduction techniques.

374 The original ICP algorithm was not designed for clustering heterogeneous scRNA-seq
375 datasets, and consequently, it tends to emphasise technical noise or batch effects, de-
376 spite the implemented ensemble clustering approach. Therefore, we adapted here the
377 ICP algorithm to perform divisive clustering rounds in order to promote the batch label
378 mixture and cell type separation (Extended Data Fig. 1B-E). Briefly, we begin with two
379 clusters determined by the cell distribution across the first principal component, in a

380 batch-wise manner (Extended Data Fig. 1B). For every epoch, i.e., a single model iter-
381 ation through the training set, the ICP algorithm selects for training the clusters those
382 cells that represent the batch-wise k nearest neighbours with the highest probability
383 (Extended Data Fig. 1C). Once the algorithm converges to a stable clustering, the next
384 clustering round starts by splitting every cluster obtained into two based on the batch-
385 wise cluster probability distribution (Extended Data Fig. 1D). The process (Extended
386 Data Fig. 1C-D) is repeated until the algorithm reaches the last clustering round (by
387 default clustering round four, corresponding to 16 target clusters; Extended Data Fig.
388 1E).

389 To demonstrate how the Coralysis multi-level integration works in practice, we used two
390 10X scRNA-seq datasets of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) obtained with
391 two different 3' assays (V1 and V2). The dataset V2 comprised ≈ 1.7 times more cells
392 than V1 (8,276 versus 4,770 cells), making this an unbalanced integration task, which
393 are typically more challenging (Fig. 1A). The divisive ICP clustering run number two
394 ($L=2$) corresponding to the cluster probability table (at $K16$) with the highest standard
395 deviation was selected to exemplify the evolution of batch label mixing and cell type
396 separation across one divisive ICP run (the algorithm was run 50 times). As expected,
397 the median cluster probability decreased throughout the divisive ICP clustering rounds,
398 i.e., $K2 \rightarrow K4 \rightarrow K8 \rightarrow K16$ (Fig. 1B). The batch label distribution per cluster was
399 dominated by cells coming from the assay V2, as expected, given the fact it comprised
400 almost twice the number of cells compared to assay V1 (Fig. 1C). The only exception
401 was cluster 8, which consisted mainly of CD16+ monocytes at $K16$ (Fig. 1D). Inter-

402 estingly, CD16+ monocytes were the only cell type with more cells in dataset V1 than
403 V2 (332 versus 225, respectively). This highlights the ability of Coralysis to handle the
404 integration of unbalanced datasets and cell types.

405 The clusters at $K2$ separated monocytes, dendritic cells (DCs), natural killer (NK), and
406 B cells from T cells (Fig. 1D). This separation was also observed in the t -SNE projec-
407 tion of the concatenated cluster probability matrices at $K2$ across the 50 independent
408 ICP runs (Fig. 1E). Noticeably, the expression of the top three positive gene coeffi-
409 cients for the ICP model corresponded to *BLVRB*, *FGFBP2* and *CD79A*, confined to
410 monocytes/DCs, NK, and B cells, respectively (Fig. 1F, Extended Data Fig. 2A and
411 Supplementary Table 1).

412 At $K4$, the first cluster gives rise to a B cell (naive and memory) and a monocyte/DC
413 cluster (CD14+ and CD16+ monocytes and activated DCs) (Fig. 1D and F). The sec-
414 ond cluster is partitioned into an effector CD8/NK and a CD8/CD4 (naive and mem-
415 ory) T cell cluster. This division is supported by coefficients of the ICP model, in-
416 cluding well-known cell type-specific genes for B cells (*MS4A1*, *CD79B/A*, *TCL1A*,
417 *LINC00926*, HLA class II histocompatibility antigen genes); monocytes/DCs (*CFP*,
418 *CFD*, *TYMP*, *AIF1*, *FCN1*, *S100A8*, *SAT1*, *LST1*, *CST3*, *CSTA*); effector CD8/NK
419 cells (*LYAR*, *APMAP*, granzymes (GZMB/H/M), *FGFBP2*, *CMC1*, chemokines (*CCL5*,
420 *XCL2*), *CTSW*); and CD4/8 naive/memory cells (*LEF1*, *IL7R*, *LDHB*, *NOSIP*, *LDL*-
421 *RAP1*, *LTB*, *NPM1*, *SPOCK2*, *IL32*, *CD3D*) (Fig. 1F, Extended Data Fig. 2B and
422 Supplementary Table 1).

423 At $K8$, B memory and plasmacytoid DCs separated from B naive cells, and similarly

424 CD14+ monocytes separated from CD16+ monocytes and activated DCs (aDCs) (Fig.
425 1D-F, Extended Data Fig. 2C and Supplementary Table 1). The other four clusters
426 involved mostly CD8 effector cells, NK cells, CD4 memory cells, and CD4 naive cells,
427 respectively. At *K16*, the clusters were further divided into separate B memory cells
428 (*MS4A1*, *CD79A/B*) from pDCs (*IRF7*, *XBP1*, *LILRA4*) and aDCs (*FCER1A*, *CD1C*)
429 from CD16+ monocytes (*FCGR3A*) despite the uneven number of cells comprising
430 these cell types (Fig. 1D-F, Extended Data Fig. 2D and Supplementary Table 1). Tran-
431 scriptionally similar cell types were also further separated, such as NK cells (*GNLY*,
432 *KLRD1*, *GZMK*, *CD63*) from CD8 effector cells (*GZMH/K/M*, *KLRG1*, *CCL5*, *CST7*).
433 These results demonstrate the sensitivity of Coralysis to integrate cell populations by
434 selecting low-to-high resolution cell type-specific gene coefficients along the top-down
435 clustering process.

436 **3.2 Coralysis prioritises bio-conservation**

437 We benchmarked Coralysis using the publicly available scib-pipeline⁵ in order to per-
438 form an independent and unbiased comparison. The top five unsupervised integra-
439 tion methods from the benchmark conducted by Luecken *et al.*⁵ were selected for the
440 comparison (scVI¹³, Scanorama¹², Seurat v4 RPCA²⁸, Harmony⁶ and fastMNN¹⁰). Ad-
441 ditionally, we included the widely used Seurat v4 CCA method²⁸. The methods were
442 benchmarked across four real datasets (pancreas, lung atlas, human immune, hu-
443 man/mouse immune) and two simulations. We used the same type of input (with and
444 without highly variable gene (HVG) selection and with or without scaling) and output

445 (batch-corrected gene expression matrix and/or embedding), datasets ($n=6$), and per-
446 formance metrics ($n=14$) as the original benchmark study⁵. In total, the scib-pipeline
447 ran 210 tasks. Eleven of these failed: Coralysis given the HVG unscaled gene ex-
448 pression matrix as input for the simulation 1 dataset; Seurat v4 CCA given the full
449 scaled gene expression matrix as input for the lung atlas and human/mouse immune
450 datasets; and all the Seurat v4 RPCA tasks for the human/mouse immune and simula-
451 tion 2 datasets (Extended Data Fig. 3A-B).

452 The trade-off between batch correction and bio-conservation was assessed by aver-
453 aging the five batch correction and the nine bio-conservation metrics for each input
454 data and each integration method (Extended Data Fig. 3A). Coralysis performed con-
455 sistently well across the different datasets, demonstrating a competitive and balanced
456 trade-off between batch correction and biological signal preservation (Extended Data
457 Fig. 3A-C- and Supplementary Fig. 1-6). In general, the differences observed in the
458 performance between the datasets reflected the complexity of the integration tasks.
459 The human pancreas data consisted of the same tissue (pancreatic islets) analysed
460 using distinct single-cell library preparation methods, the lung atlas included transcrip-
461 tionally similar but functionally different cell types from the lung airway and parenchyma
462 (Supplementary Fig. 7A-B), while the human and cross-species immune datasets rep-
463 resented more complex integration challenges with multiple batches, tissues (blood
464 and bone marrow) (Supplementary Fig. 7C), and even organisms (human and mouse)
465 (Supplementary Fig. 7D). Among the two simulation scenarios, the simulation 2 in-
466 cluded more batches and fewer clusters of transcriptionally similar identities than sim-

467 ulation 1 (Supplementary Fig. 8A-B). Thus, it is not surprising that the benchmarked
468 methods performed generally better in simulation 1 than in simulation 2 (Extended Data
469 Fig. 3A-B and Supplementary Fig. 5,6).

470 Another important aspect of Coralysis is the small variation in its performance with
471 respect to the input provided, compared with the other methods (Extended Data Fig.
472 3D). Importantly, Coralysis avoided the integration of similar yet distinct cell types (Ex-
473 tended Data Fig. 4-5). For example, in the human immune data, Coralysis was able
474 to separate CD14+ from CD16+ monocytes and NK from NKT cells (Extended Data
475 Fig. 4C). Higher bio-conservation metrics of Coralysis, such as cell type ASW (aver-
476 age silhouette width) and isolated labels (F1 and silhouette), (Extended Data Fig. 3B)
477 supported these observations. Cell type ASW measures the density and separation
478 of cell types, while the isolated label metrics assess the ability to integrate cell types
479 shared by only a few batches. This highlights the potential of Coralysis to outperform
480 current top-performing integration methods in tasks where subtle biological variation
481 and/or uneven distribution of cell types across batches need to be integrated.

482 **3.3 Coralysis outperforms in integration of unshared similar cell** 483 **types**

484 To further investigate the hypothesis that Coralysis outperforms the top-performing inte-
485 gration methods in tasks involving uneven or unshared, but transcriptionally similar cell
486 types, we envisioned three possible scenarios for unshared cell types across batches
487 (Fig. 2A): cell type unique to one of the batches, cell types unique to both batches

488 that are transcriptionally distinct, and cell types unique to both batches that are tran-
489 scriptionally similar. Since Scanorama, Seurat v4 CCA/RPCA, fastMNN, and Harmony
490 perform integration in the joint low-dimensional space, they may overlook subtle bio-
491 logical differences that are not well preserved in a reduced feature space, compared
492 to probabilistic models like Coralysis or scVI. Accordingly, although integration tasks
493 involving the first two scenarios are unlikely to be wrongly integrated, it is likely that
494 transcriptionally similar cell types will incorrectly correspond to mutual nearest neigh-
495 bours.

496 We investigated this hypothesis using a dataset of two human PBMC samples: resting
497 cells (CTRL) and interferon-stimulated cells (STIM) (Fig. 2B and Supplementary Fig.
498 9). Specifically, we considered two pairs of similar cell types CD4 naive and CD4 mem-
499 ory T cells, and CD14 and CD16 monocytes. In the CTRL sample, we retained CD16
500 monocytes and CD4 memory T cells but dropped out CD14 monocytes and CD4 naive
501 T cells. In the STIM sample, we retained and dropped out vice versa. Coralysis was
502 the only method that could clearly separate CD14 from CD16 monocytes as well as
503 naive from memory CD4 T cells (Fig. 2B and Supplementary Fig. 9,10). Despite using
504 a probabilistic model, scVI performed poorly, contrary to our expectations (Fig. 2B and
505 Supplementary Fig. 9,10). This result supports our hypothesis, showing that Coralysis
506 is a more suitable method for integrating unshared similar cell types.

507 **3.4 Coralysis integrates heterogeneous single-cell proteomics datasets**

508 Although Coralysis has been developed with the purpose of integrating and/or clus-
509 tering single-cell transcriptomic datasets, the method can also be applied to other
510 single-cell modalities. To demonstrate this, we decided to apply Coralysis integration
511 on single-cell proteomic data from two fast-evolving technologies: antibody derived
512 tags (ADT) and cytometry by time of flight (CyTOF). The ADT data consisted of human
513 PBMC samples from eight HIV-infected donors (P1-8) published by Hao *et al.*²⁸, col-
514 lected along three time points to follow both vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals
515 (228 proteins across 161,764 cells). The normalised data was integrated across two
516 batches: the first comprising donors P1-4, and the second, donors P5-8 (Fig. 3A),
517 as defined in Koca & Sevilgen²⁷, based on the eight higher-level cell type labels avail-
518 able from the same study (Fig. 3B), Coralysis integrated all cell populations well (Fig.
519 3C-D). The high granularity observed independent of the batch (Fig. 3C,E) motivated
520 us to further look into the more granular cell populations using the fine-grained cell
521 type annotations from the original study (at level 2 of granularity), which had been
522 obtained using CITE-seq with both ADT plus RNA-seq data modalities²⁸ (Fig. 3E,F).
523 Interestingly, several of the Louvain clusters identified with the Coralysis integrated
524 embedding using only the ADT data matched the fine-grained cell populations iden-
525 tified with CITE-seq multi-modal data (Fig. 3F,G), for example, clusters 13 (MAIT),
526 21 (CD16 Mono), 23 (pDC), 18 plus 24 (gdT), and 30 (platelet) (Fig. 3F,G). Further-
527 more, despite the reduced feature space (228 proteins), Coralysis was able to preserve
528 the differentiation trajectory, from naive to effector cell states, observed in B cells and

529 CD4/CD8 T cells (Fig. 3F). These results were supported by the quantification of ob-
530 jective bio-conservation and batch-correction metrics, showing a great improvement in
531 batch correction without compromising bio-conservation for any of the ground-truth cell
532 type labels (Fig. 3H and Supplementary Fig. 11).

533 The CyTOF datasets consisted of human whole blood samples published by Rahil *et*
534 *al.*²⁹ and Bjornson-Hooper *et al.*³⁰, including 35 donors infected with H1N1 influenza
535 across 11 time points (h1n1 dataset, 39 proteins across 102,147 cells), and sam-
536 ples from 86 healthy individuals stimulated with IFN γ (ifng dataset, 39 proteins across
537 114,175 cells) (Fig. 3I,J). As shown in the integrated UMAP projections (Fig. 3K,L),
538 Coralysis successfully integrated all immune cell types, including the less abundant
539 basophils (0.5% of the cells - 1,075 cells), across the highly heterogeneous CyTOF
540 datasets. These results were further supported by the improved bio-conservation and
541 batch-correction scores when compared to the unintegrated baseline (Fig. 3M). Over-
542 all, these results demonstrated that Coralysis can accurately integrate single-cell pro-
543 teomics data, even with a low number of features, such as CyTOF.

544 **3.5 Coralysis achieves high reference-mapping accuracy under** 545 **diverse query-reference scenarios**

546 The ICP models generated by training a single-cell dataset with Coralysis can be used
547 to predict the cluster identities of related, unannotated single-cell datasets, thereby
548 enabling reference-mapping. To understand the strengths and limitations of Coraly-
549 sis reference-mapping method, we assessed its accuracy across four query-reference

550 scenarios: 1) imbalanced cell types, 2) unshared cell types, 3) unrepresented batches,
551 and 4) a varied strength of the batch effect.

552 To assess the performance of Coralysis under the first two scenarios of imbalanced
553 and unshared cell types, two PBMC samples from Maan *et al.*²² were used; the batch
554 1 sample of the data was used as the reference, and batch 2 as the query. Both sam-
555 ples consisted of six cell types (B cells, CD4 T cells, CD8 T cells, CD14 monocytes,
556 FCGR3A monocytes, and NK cells), with each cell type containing the same number
557 of cells ($n = 200$). For the imbalanced cell-types scenario, we iteratively down-sampled
558 each cell type in the reference to 10% and predicted the cell type labels by projecting
559 against the reference after training with ICP (Extended Data Fig. 6A). The centroid
560 cross-batch distance (Euclidean) in the PCA space between the reference and query
561 cell types was quantified to highlight their differences across the cell types (Extended
562 Data Fig. 6B). This is particularly important since the Coralysis reference-mapping
563 method relies on the distances between query cell types projected onto the reference
564 PCA to classify cell types. As expected, the closest query cell-type centroid to each
565 reference cell-type centroid corresponded to the cell type matching the reference cell-
566 type label (Extended Data Fig. 6B). The overall accuracy ranged between 85-96%
567 (Extended Data Fig. 6C), being lowest for CD8 T cells and highest for B cells (Ex-
568 tended Data Fig. 6D-E). The accuracies were consistently lower for the down-sampled
569 cell types, particularly for CD8 T cells (Extended Data Fig. 6C and Supplementary Fig.
570 12A-F). Most of the CD8 T cell misclassifications were against CD4 T cells (Extended
571 Data Fig. 6D), likely due to their transcriptional similarity, which was reflected in the

572 smallest centroid cross-batch distance observed between the reference and query cell
573 types (Extended Data Fig. 6C). Interestingly, the lowest Coralysis confidence scores
574 for this classification task, corresponding to the proportion of K neighbors from the
575 winning class, were associated with the CD8 T cell misclassifications (Extended Data
576 Fig. 6D).

577 In the unshared cell-types scenario, we conducted a similar analysis but, instead of
578 downsampling, each reference cell type was iteratively ablated (Extended Data Fig.
579 7A-B). The classification accuracy dropped compared to the previous scenario, rang-
580 ing between 80-82% (Extended Data Fig. 7C), primarily due to the absence of the
581 ablated cell type in the reference. This led to misclassifications against the closest
582 reference cell type (Extended Data Fig. 7B and Supplementary Fig. 13A-F). Overall
583 accuracy was lowest when B cells were ablated, and highest when CD14 monocytes
584 were ablated (Extended Data Fig. 7D-E). In the absence of these cell types in the
585 reference, B cells and CD14 monocytes were mostly classified against the closest ref-
586 erence cell-type centroids, CD4 T cells and FCGR3A monocytes (also known as CD16
587 monocytes), respectively (Extended Data Fig. 7B,D-E).

588 In the unrepresented batch scenario, we built a reference of pancreatic islets by in-
589 tegrating six pancreatic scRNA-seq datasets from several technologies with Coralysis
590 (Fig. 4A-B). The queries consisted of two pancreatic scRNA-seq datasets: indrop2
591 (1,724 cells), which was represented in the reference, and smartseq2 (2,394 cells),
592 which was absent from the reference (Fig. 4C-D). The prediction accuracy was very
593 high (approximately 98%), regardless of batch representation in the reference (Fig. 4E-

594 H). Similarly, the confidence scores were high (Fig. 4E,G).

595 Finally, we tested the impact of varying strengths of batch effect on the reference-
596 mapping accuracy of Coralys. The same resting and interferon-stimulated PBMC
597 samples from Kang *et al.*²⁶ described in section 3.3 were chosen to represent this sce-
598 nario. The reference consisted of resting cells (6,548 cells) and the query of interferon-
599 stimulated PBMCs (7,451 cells). A PCA comprising the cells from both samples was
600 computed to highlight the transcriptomic variation between cell types (Extended Data
601 Fig. 8A). The variation observed along Principal Component 2 (PC2) was explained
602 by the transcriptomic response to interferon stimulation, which was stronger for mono-
603 cytes and DCs than for NK, T, and B cells (Extended Data Fig. 8A). To illustrate this
604 more clearly, the distances between the reference and query cell type centroids were
605 depicted in a heatmap, highlighting the cell type-to-cell type distances (Extended Data
606 Fig. 8B). Monocytes and DCs were the most dissimilar cell types, showing a clear sep-
607 aration from the remaining cell types, which were more similar to each other (Extended
608 Data Fig. 8B). The correspondence between ground-truth cell labels and Coralys pre-
609 dictions was high, with an overall accuracy close to 90%. The exception was a fraction
610 of CD4 memory T cells that were wrongly predicted as CD4 naive T cells (Extended
611 Data Fig. 8C-F). Importantly, the accuracy of classification for cell types that responded
612 more strongly to interferon stimulation, such as monocytes and DCs (Extended Data
613 Fig. 8A), remained high. Instead, the accuracy depended more on the similarity be-
614 tween the query and reference cell types (Extended Data Fig. 8B), with CD4 memory T
615 cells being most difficult to predict due to their transcriptional similarity with CD4 naive

616 T cells (Extended Data Fig. 8E-F). The low confidence scores in the overlapping neigh-
617 bourhoods highlighted those cell predictions that should be more carefully inspected
618 (Extended Data Fig. 8F). In summary, Coralysis accurately maps cells across distinct
619 query-reference scenarios, as long as the reference faithfully represents the query.

620 **3.6 Coralysis identifies rare cell populations previously missed in** 621 **PBMCs**

622 We next sought to take a closer look at the ability of Coralysis to identify fine-grained
623 cell populations across heterogeneous scRNA-seq datasets. For this purpose, we
624 selected nine PBMC datasets sequenced using different technologies³². As the ref-
625 erence, we selected one of the samples, which was sequenced using 10x Chromium
626 (v2) A, whereas the remaining eight samples were used as queries (sequenced using
627 10x Chromium (v2), 10x Chromium (v2) B, 10x Chromium (v3), CEL-Seq2, Drop-seq,
628 inDrops, Seq-Well, Smart-seq2). The 27,753 query cells were successfully mapped
629 onto the 3,222 reference cells (Fig. 5A), with only minor disagreement between the
630 ground-truth (Fig. 5B) and predicted cell labels (Fig. 5C). The mean accuracy per
631 query dataset was 84% (Fig. 5D). Not surprisingly, all the 10x Chromium samples
632 were above the mean as they came from the same technology as the reference. The
633 accuracy decreased gradually from the droplet-based (Drop-seq, inDrops) to the plate-
634 based datasets (Smart-seq2, CEL-Seq2, Seq-Well) (Fig. 5D). The distribution of con-
635 fidence scores for correct and incorrect classifications was similar across datasets.
636 Correct classifications showed a high peak close to one, whereas the incorrect clas-

637 sifications reached a smaller peak right after 0.5, generally followed by a uniform dis-
638 tribution towards one (Fig. 5E). These results support the use of confidence scores
639 as a measure of classification reliability, particularly for scores below 0.75, where the
640 distribution of incorrect classifications exceeds that of correct classifications.

641 We next inspected the reason for the lowest accuracy observed with the Seq-Well
642 dataset. Encouragingly, all the predicted cell types were supported by the expression
643 of their respective marker genes (Fig. 5F). Therefore, we then investigated whether the
644 low accuracy could be due to originally wrong classifications, as the Seq-Well dataset
645 comprised only seven cell types, while nine cell types were predicted (Fig. 5G-H). In-
646 deed, Coralysis identified two rare populations in the dataset – CD16+ monocytes and
647 natural killer cells – that had previously been completely missed. The identification
648 of CD16+ monocytes, which were previously misclassified as CD14+ monocytes, was
649 supported by the expression of *FCGR3A* (also known as *CD16*), but not *CD14*. Simi-
650 larly, the appearance of natural killer cells was supported by the expression of *KIR2DL3*
651 but not *CD3D*, a marker of cytotoxic T cells (Fig. 5I). These results demonstrated the
652 ability of Coralysis to identify previously missed rare cell populations.

653 **3.7 Coralysis cell cluster probabilities enable cell state identifica-** 654 **tion**

655 Finally, we explored the applicability of the Coralysis cell cluster probabilities for infer-
656 ring cell states and their differential expression programs. The Coralysis cell cluster
657 probability corresponds to the likelihood that a cell belongs to its assigned cluster. This

658 probability serves as a measure of confidence of the cluster assignment and as a proxy
659 for similarity. Therefore, we hypothesized that highly distinct cells, representing termi-
660 nally differentiated or steady states, would exhibit higher probabilities, while transient or
661 intermediate cells would show lower probabilities, as they represent cells transitioning
662 between steady states.

663 To test our hypothesis, we ran Coralys on differentiating human bone marrow CD34+
664 cells from Persad *et al.*³⁴ (Fig. 6A). In agreement with our expectations, the Coralys
665 cell cluster probabilities were higher for terminally differentiated cells, such as ery-
666 throid, lymphoid, dendritic, and monocyte cell lineages, and lower for transient, fast-
667 transitioning cells like hematopoietic stem cells and hematopoietic multipotent progen-
668 itor cells (Fig. 6B). This observation was supported by the positive Pearson correlation
669 ($\rho=0.73$) between Coralys cell cluster probability and Palantir pseudotime (Fig. 6C).

670 Next, we integrated 31,029 embryonic stem cells from a developing human embryoid
671 body, generated by Moon *et al.*³⁶, with Coralys to study the local distribution of cell
672 cluster probabilities throughout the differentiation process (Fig. 6D,E; annotations used
673 as given in Weiler *et al.*³⁷). As expected, terminally differentiated cells such as neural
674 crest (NC), endoderm-1 (EN-1), cardiac precursors (CPs), neuronal subtype-1 (NS-1),
675 or hemangioblast, had higher cell cluster probabilities (Fig. 6F). Notably, Coralys pre-
676 served inter-stage transcriptomic differences, as exemplified by embryonic stem cells
677 and neural crest cells, despite integrating cells by embryonic stage (Fig. 6D,E). This
678 further highlighted the ability of Coralys to identify similar cell types across unbal-
679 anced datasets while preserving local biological differences.

680 Interestingly, Coralysis cell cluster probabilities were able to discriminate within-cell
681 type differences across embryonic stages for several cell types, with cells progress-
682 ing from low to high probabilities as they transitioned from early to late developmental
683 stages (Fig. 6G).

684 Overall, these observations supported the applicability of Coralysis cell cluster proba-
685 bilities for inferring cell states and their differential gene expression programs, which are
686 expected to be stage-dependent, with early-stage cells being more immature and pro-
687 liferative compared to mature cells at later stages. To demonstrate this, we divided the
688 Coralysis cell cluster probabilities into 20 evenly sized bins separately for each cell type
689 and calculated the Pearson correlation between the average cell cluster probability and
690 the average gene expression across the bins to identify stage-specific genes. Among
691 the top five negatively (early) and positively (late) correlated genes per cell type were
692 genes related to cell cycle (e.g., *CDK1*, *CDKN3*), proliferation (e.g., *MALAT1*, *PTMA*),
693 migration (e.g., *S100A10*), and differentiation (e.g., *CKB*, *ANXA2/5*) (see Supplemen-
694 tary Fig. 14). For instance, mesoderm and endoderm (EN-1) cells showed a good
695 correlation between early to late developmental stages with cell cluster probability bins
696 allowing for a better resolution over their differential gene expression programs (Fig.
697 6H,M). Among the top early genes for mesoderm cells, the transmembrane protein 88
698 (*TMEM88*) is known to inhibit the *Wnt*/ β -catenin signaling pathway in order to allow the
699 commitment of pre-cardiac mesoderm cells into cardiomyocytes³⁸ (Fig. 6I-K). Notably,
700 this was supported by the co-localisation of *TMEM88*-expressing cells with epicardial
701 and cardiac precursors (EPs and CPs; Fig. 6E). Additionally, glycolysis-related genes,

702 such as *LDHB*, which was upregulated in late mesoderm cells, have shown differen-
703 tial expression across developmental stages in mesoderm during mouse gastrulation³⁹
704 (Fig. 6L). Finally, in agreement with our findings, Vianello & Lutolf⁴⁰ found *SFRP1* and
705 *IGFBP5*, the latter functionally similar to *IGFBP6*, as being upregulated in early and
706 late endoderm, respectively (Fig. 6N-Q). Overall, these results highlighted the ability
707 of Coralysis to identify functionally relevant cell states and their differential expression
708 programs.

709 4 Discussion

710 In this study, we present Coralysis, a method for sensitive integration, reference-mapping,
711 and cell state identification across single-cell datasets through multi-level integration.
712 It relies on an adapted version of our previously introduced Iterative Clustering Projec-
713 tion¹⁵ (ICP) algorithm to identify shared cell clusters across heterogeneous datasets
714 by leveraging multiple rounds of divisive clustering. Similar to assembling a “puzzle”,
715 multi-level integration enables ICP to blend the batch effects and separate cell types
716 by focusing on low- to high-level features (see Fig. 1 and Extended Data Fig. 2). The
717 trained ICP models can then be used for various purposes, including prediction of clus-
718 ter identities of related, unannotated single-cell datasets through reference-mapping,
719 and inference of cell states and their differential expression programs using the cell
720 cluster probabilities that represent the likelihood of each cell belonging to each clus-
721 ter. Coralysis performed consistently well across a wide range of integration tasks
722 compared to current top-performing integration methods. It prioritises bio-conservation
723 over batch correction, outperforming existing methods in integration tasks involving

724 datasets that do not share similar cell-types. Furthermore, Coralysis exhibited minimal
725 variation in performance based on input data type, partly due to its inherent feature
726 extraction procedure, which employs $L1$ -regularized logistic regression¹⁵.
727 The feature extraction procedure of Coralysis is particularly relevant for the detection
728 of diseased or perturbed cell states and rare populations, as feature selection methods
729 might overlook features required to discriminate these. For example, the commonly
730 used Seurat highly variable gene selection method relies largely on lowly expressed
731 genes with high coefficients of variation representing technical noise that masks sub-
732 tle cellular variation⁴¹. Furthermore, Coralysis allows the retrieval of gene coefficients
733 from ICP models for a given ICP run or clustering label using a majority voting ap-
734 proach. This offers the advantage of identifying cluster marker genes independently
735 from differential expression analysis avoiding the bias towards highly expressed genes
736 representing false-positives^{42,43}. Notably, logistic regression, which is at the core of
737 ICP, was one of the best methods for identifying cluster markers among 59 recently
738 benchmarked tools⁴⁴.
739 As the complexity of cell atlases increases in terms of tissue, time, and condition rep-
740 resentation, subtle biological differences can become difficult to dissociate from batch
741 effects, likely increasing the demand for such integration functionalities. The appli-
742 cation of Coralysis is not limited to single-cell transcriptomics; it can also be applied
743 to integrate data from other single-cell assays, such as antibody-derived tags (ADT)
744 or cytometry by time of flight (CyTOF), within the exciting and rapidly evolving field
745 of single-cell proteomics (Fig. 3). The reduced feature space of these assays, typi-

746 cally ranging from dozens to a few hundred, did not prevent Coralys from identifying
747 fine-grained cell populations and preserving differentiation trajectories, nor from de-
748 tecting rare populations, such as basophils (0.5%), in whole blood CyTOF data. The
749 identification of cell populations at high resolution provided by Coralys is expected to
750 be of great value as unbiased measurements of single-cell proteomes become more
751 common with advancements in mass spectrometry⁴⁵. In the future, we aim to extend
752 the application of the Coralys integration method to other single-cell assays, such as
753 ATAC-seq, and even across different modalities with shared features by testing differ-
754 ent regularizations (e.g., Ridge instead of LASSO) and data input transformations.
755 Coralys also allows to avoid cumbersome *de novo* integration when a reference
756 trained with Coralys exists. Reference-mapping is becoming routine as projects like
757 the Human Cell Atlas⁴⁶ or the Tabula Muris⁴⁷ work to decipher the identities of mil-
758 lions of cells. Robust methods are needed to accurately map, for instance, diseased
759 cells against healthy references, perturbed cells, or cells generated by new single-
760 cell technologies. Here, we demonstrated that Coralys performs well across several
761 query-reference scenarios, including cell-type imbalance, batch representation, or var-
762 ied batch strength. We also showed the applicability of Coralys to identify previously
763 missed rare cell populations across query-reference datasets originating from different
764 sequencing technologies. Additionally, the confidence scores provided help for the user
765 to identify which cell type predictions should be more carefully inspected. Although
766 Coralys currently has limitations in detecting cells not represented in the reference,
767 this is unlikely to pose a hurdle as references become increasingly comprehensive.

768 Future developments should address this limitation, for instance, by comparing the
769 similarity between query and reference model coefficients.

770 A long-standing challenge in single-cell biology is the definition of cell type versus cell
771 state and how to identify and distinguish them. Cell states correspond to discrete
772 modes that a given cell type can assume under different stimuli⁴⁸. As such, they share
773 a common gene expression program, which places them under the same cell type ‘um-
774 brella’ definition. For example, the CD8+ T cell type can assume the naive, memory,
775 or effector CD8+ T cell states. Coralys cell cluster probability aids the identification
776 of terminally differentiated and transient cell types. Similarly to ‘metacells’, cell cluster
777 probability bins aggregate highly similar cells, representing primarily technical noise,
778 and captures existing biological variation within cell types across bins. This can help
779 unravel cell states and their differential expression programs, such as those involved in
780 early to late embryoid cell development or healthy versus diseased cells. We anticipate
781 that Coralys will advance the catalog of cell heterogeneity by improving the integra-
782 tion of imbalanced cell types and states, enabling a more faithful representation of the
783 cellular landscape in complex single-cell experiments.

784 References

- 785 1. Smolander, J., Junttila, S., Venäläinen, M. S. & Elo, L. L. scShaper: an ensemble
786 method for fast and accurate linear trajectory inference from single-cell RNA-seq
787 data. *Bioinformatics* **38**, 1328–1335 (2022).
- 788 2. Junttila, S., Smolander, J. & Elo, L. L. Benchmarking methods for detecting dif-
789 ferential states between conditions from multi-subject single-cell RNA-seq data.
790 *Briefings in Bioinformatics* **23**. bbac286. ISSN: 1477-4054. eprint: [https://academic.](https://academic.oup.com/bib/article-pdf/23/5/bbac286/45936028/bbac286.pdf)
791 [oup.com/bib/article-pdf/23/5/bbac286/45936028/bbac286.pdf](https://academic.oup.com/bib/article-pdf/23/5/bbac286/45936028/bbac286.pdf). [https :](https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbac286)
792 [//doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbac286](https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbac286) (July 2022).
- 793 3. Tran, H. T. N. *et al.* A benchmark of batch-effect correction methods for single-cell
794 RNA sequencing data. *Genome biology* **21**, 1–32 (2020).
- 795 4. Richards, L. M. *et al.* A comparison of data integration methods for single-cell
796 RNA sequencing of cancer samples. *bioRxiv*. eprint: [https://www.biorxiv.](https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2021/08/06/2021.08.04.453579.full.pdf)
797 [org/content/early/2021/08/06/2021.08.04.453579.full.pdf](https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2021/08/06/2021.08.04.453579.full.pdf). [https :](https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2021/08/06/2021.08.04.453579)
798 [//www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2021/08/06/2021.08.04.453579](https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2021/08/06/2021.08.04.453579) (2021).
- 799 5. Luecken, M. D. *et al.* Benchmarking atlas-level data integration in single-cell ge-
800 nomics. *Nature methods* **19**, 41–50 (2022).
- 801 6. Korsunsky, I. *et al.* Fast, sensitive and accurate integration of single-cell data with
802 Harmony. *Nature methods* **16**, 1289–1296 (2019).
- 803 7. Welch, J. D. *et al.* Single-cell multi-omic integration compares and contrasts fea-
804 tures of brain cell identity. *Cell* **177**, 1873–1887 (2019).

- 805 8. Stuart, T. *et al.* Comprehensive integration of single-cell data. *Cell* **177**, 1888–
806 1902 (2019).
- 807 9. Andreatta, M. & Carmona, S. J. STACAS: Sub-Type Anchor Correction for Align-
808 ment in Seurat to integrate single-cell RNA-seq data. *Bioinformatics* **37**, 882–884
809 (2021).
- 810 10. Haghverdi, L., Lun, A. T., Morgan, M. D. & Marioni, J. C. Batch effects in single-
811 cell RNA-sequencing data are corrected by matching mutual nearest neighbors.
812 *Nature biotechnology* **36**, 421–427 (2018).
- 813 11. Xu, C. *et al.* Probabilistic harmonization and annotation of single-cell transcrip-
814 tomics data with deep generative models. *Molecular systems biology* **17**, e9620
815 (2021).
- 816 12. Hie, B., Bryson, B. & Berger, B. Efficient integration of heterogeneous single-cell
817 transcriptomes using Scanorama. *Nature biotechnology* **37**, 685–691 (2019).
- 818 13. Lopez, R., Regier, J., Cole, M. B., Jordan, M. I. & Yosef, N. Deep generative
819 modeling for single-cell transcriptomics. *Nature methods* **15**, 1053–1058 (2018).
- 820 14. Argelaguet, R., Cuomo, A. S., Stegle, O. & Marioni, J. C. Computational principles
821 and challenges in single-cell data integration. *Nature biotechnology* **39**, 1202–
822 1215 (2021).
- 823 15. Smolander, J., Junttila, S., Venäläinen, M. S. & Elo, L. L. ILoReg: a tool for high-
824 resolution cell population identification from single-cell RNA-seq data. *Bioinfor-*
825 *matics* **37**, 1107–1114 (2021).

- 826 16. Lun, A. T. L., McCarthy, D. J. & Marioni, J. C. A step-by-step workflow for low-
827 level analysis of single-cell RNA-seq data with Bioconductor. *F1000Res*. **5**, 2122
828 (2016).
- 829 17. Baglama, J., Reichel, L. & Lewis, B. W. *irlba: Fast Truncated Singular Value De-*
830 *composition and Principal Components Analysis for Large Dense and Sparse Ma-*
831 *trices* R package version 2.3.5 (2021). [https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=irlba)
832 [irlba](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=irlba).
- 833 18. Arthur, D., Vassilvitskii, S., *et al.* *k-means++: The advantages of careful seeding*
834 *in Soda 7* (2007), 1027–1035.
- 835 19. Arya, S., Mount, D., Kemp, S. E. & Jefferis, G. *RANN: Fast Nearest Neighbour*
836 *Search (Wraps ANN Library) Using L2 Metric* R package version 2.6.1 (2019).
837 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=RANN>.
- 838 20. R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing* R Foun-
839 *ndation for Statistical Computing* (Vienna, Austria, 2022). [https://www.R-project.](https://www.R-project.org/)
840 [org/](https://www.R-project.org/).
- 841 21. Venables, W. N. & Ripley, B. D. *Modern Applied Statistics with S* Fourth. ISBN
842 0-387-95457-0. <https://www.stats.ox.ac.uk/pub/MASS4/> (Springer, New York,
843 2002).
- 844 22. Maan, H. *et al.* Characterizing the impacts of dataset imbalance on single-cell
845 data integration. *Nature Biotechnology*, 1–10 (2024).

- 846 23. Wickham, H. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis* ISBN: 978-3-319-24277-
847 4. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org> (Springer-Verlag New York, 2016).
- 848 24. Yu, G. *scatterpie: Scatter Pie Plot* R package version 0.2.3 (2024). [https://](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=scatterpie)
849 CRAN.R-project.org/package=scatterpie.
- 850 25. Gu, Z. Complex Heatmap Visualization. *iMeta* (2022).
- 851 26. Kang, H. M. *et al.* Multiplexed droplet single-cell RNA-sequencing using natural
852 genetic variation. *Nature biotechnology* **36**, 89–94 (2018).
- 853 27. Koca, M. B. & Sevilgen, F. E. Integration of single-cell proteomic datasets through
854 distinctive proteins in cell clusters. *Proteomics* **24**, 2300282 (2024).
- 855 28. Hao, Y. *et al.* Integrated analysis of multimodal single-cell data. *Cell* **184**, 3573–
856 3587 (2021).
- 857 29. Rahil, Z. *et al.* Landscape of coordinated immune responses to H1N1 challenge
858 in humans. *The Journal of clinical investigation* **130**, 5800–5816 (2020).
- 859 30. Bjornson-Hooper, Z. B. *et al.* A comprehensive atlas of immunological differences
860 between humans, mice, and non-human primates. *Frontiers in immunology* **13**,
861 867015 (2022).
- 862 31. Melville, J. *uwot: The Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP)*
863 *Method for Dimensionality Reduction* R package version 0.1.14 (2022). [https:](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=uwot)
864 [//CRAN.R-project.org/package=uwot](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=uwot).
- 865 32. Ding, J. *et al.* Systematic comparison of single-cell and single-nucleus RNA-
866 sequencing methods. *Nature biotechnology* **38**, 737–746 (2020).

- 867 33. McCarthy, D. J., Campbell, K. R., Lun, A. T. L. & Willis, Q. F. Scater: pre-processing,
868 quality control, normalisation and visualisation of single-cell RNA-seq data in R.
869 *Bioinformatics* **33**, 1179–1186 (8 2017).
- 870 34. Persad, S. *et al.* SEACells infers transcriptional and epigenomic cellular states
871 from single-cell genomics data. *Nature Biotechnology* **41**, 1746–1757 (2023).
- 872 35. Setty, M. *et al.* Characterization of cell fate probabilities in single-cell data with
873 Palantir. *Nature biotechnology* **37**, 451–460 (2019).
- 874 36. Moon, K. R. *et al.* Visualizing structure and transitions in high-dimensional biolog-
875 ical data. *Nature biotechnology* **37**, 1482–1492 (2019).
- 876 37. Weiler, P., Lange, M., Klein, M., Pe’er, D. & Theis, F. CellRank 2: unified fate
877 mapping in multiview single-cell data. *Nature Methods*, 1–10 (2024).
- 878 38. Palpant, N. J. *et al.* Transmembrane protein 88: a Wnt regulatory protein that
879 specifies cardiomyocyte development. *Development* **140**, 3799–3808 (2013).
- 880 39. Cao, D. *et al.* Selective utilization of glucose metabolism guides mammalian gas-
881 trulation. *Nature*, 1–10 (2024).
- 882 40. Vianello, S. & Lutolf, M. In vitro endoderm emergence and self-organisation in the
883 absence of extraembryonic tissues and embryonic architecture. *BioRxiv*, 2020–
884 06 (2020).
- 885 41. Cho, J., Baik, B., Nguyen, H. C., Park, D. & Nam, D. Characterizing efficient fea-
886 ture selection for single-cell expression analysis. *Briefings in Bioinformatics* **25**,
887 bbae317 (2024).

- 888 42. Sonesson, C. & Robinson, M. D. Bias, robustness and scalability in single-cell
889 differential expression analysis. *Nature methods* **15**, 255–261 (2018).
- 890 43. Squair, J. W. *et al.* Confronting false discoveries in single-cell differential expres-
891 sion. *Nature communications* **12**, 5692 (2021).
- 892 44. Pullin, J. M. & McCarthy, D. J. A comparison of marker gene selection methods
893 for single-cell RNA sequencing data. *Genome Biology* **25**, 56 (2024).
- 894 45. Bennett, H. M., Stephenson, W., Rose, C. M. & Darmanis, S. Single-cell pro-
895 teomics enabled by next-generation sequencing or mass spectrometry. *Nature*
896 *Methods* **20**, 363–374 (2023).
- 897 46. Regev, A. *et al.* The human cell atlas. *elife* **6**, e27041 (2017).
- 898 47. Tabula Muris, C., Overall, C., Logistical, C., *et al.* Single-cell transcriptomics of 20
899 mouse organs creates a Tabula Muris. *Nature* **562**, 367–372 (2018).
- 900 48. Morris, S. A. The evolving concept of cell identity in the single cell era. *Develop-*
901 *ment* **146**, dev169748 (2019).

902 5 Acknowledgements

903 The authors thank the Elo lab for useful discussions and support. AGGS and LLE
904 were supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation pro-
905 gramme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no.: 955321. AGGS
906 was also supported by the University of Turku, Åbo Akademi University, Turku Gradu-
907 ate School (UTUGS). LLE reports grants from Research Council of Finland (310561,
908 329278, 335434, 335611, 341342, 364700), Sigrid Juselius Foundation, and Cancer
909 Foundation Finland during the conduct of the study. Our research is also supported by
910 University of Turku Graduate School (UTUGS), Biocenter Finland, and ELIXIR Finland.

911 6 Author contributions

912 AGGS conceptualised and implemented the method, performed the analyses, pre-
913 pared the figures and wrote the manuscript. JS assisted in the conceptualisation
914 and analyses. SJ assisted in the conceptualisation and analyses, tested the method,
915 critically reviewed the analyses and supervised the work. LLE conceived and super-
916 vised the study, tested the method, critically reviewed the analyses, and participated
917 in writing the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the
918 manuscript.

Figure 1 Demonstration of Coralysis multi-level integration method. **A** Unintegrated peripheral blood mononuclear cells from two 10X 3' assays, V1 ($n=4,770$ cells) and V2 ($n=8,276$ cells), projected onto t -SNE comprising activated dendritic cells (aDC), B memory cells (B memory), B naive cells, CD4 memory cells (CD4 mem), CD4 naive cells, CD8 effector T cells (CD8 eff), CD8 T cells (CD8 T), hematopoietic stem cells (HSC), megakaryocytes, monocytes, CD16⁺ monocytes, natural killer cells (NK), plasmacytoid dendritic cells (pDC) and regulatory T cells (Treg). **B** Divisive ICP clustering tree for the divisive ICP run corresponding to the *K16* cluster probability table with the highest standard deviation ($L=2$). Size of the dots represents cluster size and the colour the median cluster probability. **C** Cell distribution of batches per cluster for the divisive ICP run 2. **D** Distribution of cell types per cluster for the divisive ICP run 2. **E** t -SNE projections demonstrating multi-level integration in practice highlighting the fade of batch effect and separation of cell types along the four divisive ICP rounds (2, 4, 8 and 16). **F** Top ten positive coefficients for every cluster across the four divisive ICP rounds for the run 2. Rows represent the 16 clusters found at divisive ICP run 2 and columns coefficients, i.e., genes. The normalized gene expression data was averaged across the clusters and standardized (Z-score) cluster wise. The top three coefficients for every cluster at every round are labeled.

Figure 2 Coralysis outperforms top-performer methods for an integration task with batches with unshared similar cell type pairs. **A** Representation of mutual nearest neighbours search on the low dimensional space for integration scenarios where batches do not share all cell types: unique (one cell type is unique to one of the batches), distinct pair (one distinct pair of cell types unshared across batches, e.g., monocytes versus CD4 T cells), and similar pair (one similar pair of cell types unshared across batches, e.g., CD4 naive versus CD4 memory). **B** UMAP projections highlighting the cell-type identity before and after integration of two PBMC scRNA-seq datasets through the scib-pipeline. The two PBMC datasets consisted of one sample representing resting PBMCs (CTRL) and the other interferon-stimulated cells (STIM). CD4 naive T cells and CD14 monocytes were removed from the CTRL batch sample and CD4 memory T cells and CD16 monocytes from the STIM sample. Unshared similar cell type pairs are circumscribed by black lines. The best input-output combination was selected for every method. The label “full” represents input data with all features, and the minus and plus signs correspond to unscaled and scaled data, respectively.

Figure 3 Coralysis enables the integration of heterogeneous single-cell proteomics datasets from different technologies.

UMAP of unintegrated antibody derived tags (ADT) data of human PBMCs originally published by Hao *et al.*²⁸ highlighting **A** the batch and **B** the cell type label identities as given in Koca & Sevilgen²⁷. UMAP of the same ADT data of human PBMCs after performing integration with Coralysis highlighting **C** the batch and **D** the cell type label identities. Integrated UMAP with cells labeled as in **E** Koca & Sevilgen²⁷, as in **F** Hao *et al.*²⁸, at level 2 of granularity, and **G** with the Louvain clusters computed on the Coralysis integrated embedding. **H** Assessment of integration performed with Coralysis on the ADT data set provided by the scib-metrics python package using as ground-truth the cell type labels given in Koca & Sevilgen²⁷. UMAP of unintegrated cytometry by time of flight (CyTOF) data of whole blood from patients infected with influenza (h1n1) or cells stimulated with interferon (ifng) originally published by Rahil *et al.*²⁹ and Bjornson-Hooper *et al.*³⁰, respectively, highlighting **I** the batch and **J** the cell type label identities as given in Koca & Sevilgen²⁷. UMAP of the same CyTOF data of human blood cells after performing integration with Coralysis highlighting **K** the batch and **L** the cell type label identities. **M** Assessment of integration performed with Coralysis on the CyTOF dataset with the scib-metrics package.

Figure 4 Accuracy performance of Coralysis reference-mapping method for a query-reference scenario of an unrepresented batch. **A** Unintegrated pancreatic reference UMAP highlighting the batch - sequencing libraries - and cell type labels (left-right). **B** Integrated pancreatic reference UMAP obtained with Coralysis highlighting the respective batch and cell type labels (left-right). **C** Queries projected onto the reference integrated UMAP with Coralysis reference-mapping method. Colours highlight dataset identity, i.e., reference and query (indrop2 and smartseq2) labels (left), and ground-truth cell-type labels (right). **D** Queries projected onto the reference UMAP with reference cells removed for clarity. Colours highlight query identity and predicted cell labels (left-right). UMAP highlighting ground-truth, predictions and confidence scores for **E** indrop2 and **G** smartseq2 queries projected onto the reference UMAP. Confusion matrix of predicted versus ground-truth cell labels for **F** indrop2 and **H** smartseq2 query predictions. Top colour bar represents cell type labels. The confidence scores represent the proportion of K neighbours from the winning class ($K=10$). The values in the confusion matrices correspond to the number of cells matching each other and the values at the end of each row, the number of total misclassifications for every predicted cell type. The heatmap colors in the matrices represent the frequency of predicted cell types in percentage.

Figure 5 Coralysis identifies rare cell populations in a Seq-Well batch of peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) mapped against a 10x Chromium (v2) A reference of PBMCs scRNA-seq dataset from Ding *et al.*³². **A** Queries (right) projected onto the reference (left) UMAP. Queries consisted of eight scRNA-seq datasets of PBMCs sequenced with different technologies. The reference highlighted in light blue corresponded to a PBMC scRNA-seq data prepared with 10x Chromium (v2) A technology. **B** Reference UMAP (left) and projected queries (right) highlighting the ground-truth cell type labels as distributed through *SeuratData* software from Ding *et al.*³². **C** Reference UMAP (left) and projected queries (right) highlighting the cell type labels transferred from the reference to the queries with Coralysis reference-mapping method. **D** Bar plot of overall accuracy per query dataset. The average accuracy across the eight queries is delimited with a dashed line. **E** Density plots of correct and incorrect classifications for each query dataset. **F** Dot plot showing the expression of marker genes for the predicted PBMC cell types for the query Seq-Well. Average expression was standardized by predicted cell type (row). Proportion expressed refers to the proportion of cells expressing the marker gene in the cell type group. UMAP of the query Seq-Well projected onto the reference highlighting **G** the ground-truth cell type labels and **H** the predicted cell labels by Coralysis. **I** UMAP of query Seq-Well showing the expression of marker genes of CD14+ monocytes (*CD14*) versus CD16+ monocytes (*FCGR3A*) as well as cytotoxic T cells (*CD3D*) versus natural killer cells (*KIR2DL3*) (from left to right).

Figure 6 Coralysis cell cluster probability enables the identification of terminally differentiated cell types. UMAP projection of CD34+ bone marrow cells highlighting **A** cell type labels as given originally by Persad *et al.*³⁴ (CLP (Common Lymphoid Progenitor), HMP (Hematopoietic Multipotent Progenitor), MEP (Megakaryocyte-Erythroid Progenitor), cDC (conventional Dendritic Cells), Ery (Erythroid), HSC (Hematopoietic Stem Cells), Mono (Monocytes), pDC (plasmacytoid Dendritic Cells)) and **B** Coralysis cell cluster probability. Mean probability across the 50 independent ICP runs (i.e., $L=50$). **C** Positive correlation between Coralysis cell cluster probability and Palantir pseudotime ($\rho=0.73$) as provided in Persad *et al.*³⁴. UMAP projection of embryoid body development integrated with Coralysis highlighting **D** the embryonic stage, **E** the cell type labels as given originally by Weiler *et al.*³⁷ (CPs (Cardiac Precursors), EN (Endoderm), EPs (Epicardial Precursors), ESC (Embryonic Stem Cell), Hemangioblast, Mesoderm, NC (Neural Crest), NE (Neuroectoderm), NS (Neuronal Subtypes), Posterior EN (Posterior Endoderm), SMPs (Smooth Muscle Precursors)) and **F** the Coralysis cell cluster probability. **G** Density plots of Coralysis cell cluster probability per embryonic stage for each cell type. Mean cell cluster probability was scaled to range 0-1. **H** Distribution of mesoderm cells across embryonic stages and Coralysis cell cluster probability bins ($n=20$). In total cell cluster probability was divided into 20 bins highlighted on top of the heatmap. Cell numbers were transformed by column Z-score. **I** Expression of the top five negatively and positively correlated genes across the Coralysis cell cluster probability bins for mesoderm cells. Pearson correlation was calculated between the mean cell cluster probability and the average gene expression across the 20 bins. Top colour bar corresponds to the mean cell cluster probability per bin. The averaged gene expression is represented by Z-scores (by row). UMAP representation of mesoderm cells showing **J** cell cluster probabilities and gene expression (scaled by Z-score) of **K** *TMEM88* and **L** *LDHB*. **M** Distribution of EN-1 cells across embryonic stages and Coralysis cell cluster probability bins ($n=20$). **N** Expression of the top five negatively and positively correlated genes across the Coralysis cell cluster probability bins for EN-1 cells. UMAP representation of mesoderm cells showing **O** cell cluster probabilities and gene expression (scaled by Z-score) of **P** *SFRP1* and **Q** *IGFBP6*.

Extended Data Figure 1 Coralysis integration flowchart. **A** An input of heterogeneous scRNA-seq datasets are overclustered batch wise into a training set modelled through the Iterative Clustering Projection (ICP) algorithm in order to predict the cell cluster probabilities and obtain an integrated embedding. Adaptations to the original ICP algorithm¹⁵: **B** batch wise cluster assignment at start, dependent on the cell distribution across Principal Component 1 (median as cutoff); **C** training cells selected from batch k nearest neighbours of the cell with the highest probability for every batch per cluster; and, **D** upon ICP clustering convergence, each cluster is further divided into two for the next clustering round, dependent on the batch wise cluster probability distribution (median as cutoff). **E** Multi-level integration is achieved through multiple divisive clustering rounds, blending the batch effect and highlighting the biological signal incrementally. Shapes represent cell types and colours batches.

Extended Data Figure 2 Expression of the top three positive gene coefficients for the ICP model corresponding to the run $L=2$ projected onto t -SNE. A-D Top three positive coefficients per cluster per clustering round level $K2$ **A**, $K4$ **B**, $K8$ **C** and $K16$ **D**. The plot title highlights the cluster number and the respective gene coefficient. For every clustering round level a t -SNE was built from the concatenation of all cluster probability tables ($L=50$ ICP runs) from the respective clustering round.

Extended Data Figure 3 Benchmark of Coralysis integration method through the scib-pipeline. **A** Mean of batch-correction ($n=5$) versus bio-conservation ($n=9$) scib metrics for each method benchmarked (Coralysis, scVI, Scanorama, fastMNN, Harmony, Seurat v4 CCA/RPCA) across four real (pancreas, lung, human immune, human/mouse immune) and two simulated datasets (simulation 1 and 2). Colours represent different output-input and shapes distinct methods. Different types of output consist of an integrated embedding (embedding) or a batch-corrected gene expression matrix (genes). The different inputs included providing the gene expression data scaled (+) or unscaled (-) and with (hvg) or without (full) feature selection. **B** Individual bio-conservation and batch-correction scib metrics for each method and dataset benchmarked. Metrics were standardized (Z-score) across methods. **C** Averaged bio-conservation and batch-correction scores across the six datasets. **D** Variance in performance of integration for different input-output(s) across methods. Performance score consists of the weighted average of bio-conservation (0.6) and batch-correction (0.4) metrics.

Extended Data Figure 4 Coralys integrated UMAP projections for the four real datasets obtained through the scib-pipeline benchmark. The datasets included were pancreas, lung atlas, human immune and human/mouse immune **A-D**. The top left subtitle corresponds to the input data used (from left to right, from top to bottom): full unscaled gene expression matrix (full(-)), full scaled gene expression matrix (full(+)), highly variable genes unscaled gene expression matrix (hvg(-)) and highly variable genes scaled gene expression matrix (hvg(+)). The left and right plots for each dataset for a given input data type highlight the batch and cell type labels, respectively.

Extended Data Figure 5 Coralys integrated UMAP projections for the two simulated datasets obtained through the scib-pipeline benchmark. The datasets included were simulations 1 and 2 **A-B**. The top left subtitle corresponds to the input data used (from left to right, from top to bottom): full unscaled gene expression matrix (full(-)), full scaled gene expression matrix (full(+)), highly variable genes unscaled gene expression matrix (hvg(-)) and highly variable genes scaled gene expression matrix (hvg(+)). The left and right plots for each dataset for a given input data type highlight the batch and cell type labels, respectively. The integration task for the simulation 1 dataset, given the input hvg(-), failed.

D Coralys prediction accuracy (10% CD8 T cell): 0.846

E Coralys prediction accuracy (10% B cell): 0.961

Extended Data Figure 6 Accuracy performance of Coralysis reference-mapping method for a query-reference scenario of imbalanced cell types. **A** UMAP projection of query and reference PBMC datasets coloured by dataset (top) and cell type (bottom) identities. **B** Centroid cross-batch Euclidean distance in PCA space highlighting the similarity between cell types across batches. The distance between the same cell type across reference-query for every reference-query comparison was subtracted in the respective comparison in order to set the distance of every comparison to start from zero. **C** Cell-specific accuracy scores in down-sampled comparisons. In each reference-query comparison one cell type was down-sampled to 10%. The accuracy scores for each cell type in the same comparison are joined by the solid lines, their colours representing the down-sampled cell type. The average accuracy score for each comparison is given by the dashed line, with the two values highlighted corresponding to the lowest and highest overall accuracy (CD8 T cell-B cell). For every comparison, the darkest dot corresponds to the down-sampled cell type. Projection of query onto reference UMAP highlighting ground-truth, predictions and confidence scores obtained with Coralysis reference-mapping method for the comparisons with the lowest **D** and the highest **E** overall accuracy (CD8 T cell-B cell). The confidence scores represent the proportion of K neighbours from the winning class ($K=10$). Ellipses circumscribe the position of the down-sampled cell type.

Extended Data Figure 7 Accuracy performance of Coralysis reference-mapping method for a query-reference scenario of unshared cell types. **A** UMAP projection of query and reference PBMC datasets colored by dataset (top) and cell type (bottom) identities. **B** Centroid cross-batch Euclidean distance in PCA space highlighting the similarity between cell types across batches. The distance between the same cell type across reference-query for every reference-query comparison was subtracted in the respective comparison in order to set the distance of every comparison to start from zero. **C** Cell-specific accuracy scores in ablated comparisons. In each reference-query comparison one cell type was ablated. The accuracy scores for each cell type in the same comparison are joined by the solid lines, their colours representing the ablated cell type. The average accuracy score for each comparison is given by the dashed line, with the two values highlighted corresponding to the lowest and highest overall accuracy (B cell-CD14 monocyte). For every comparison, the darkest dot corresponds to the ablated cell type. Projection of query onto reference UMAP highlighting ground-truth, predictions and confidence scores obtained with Coralysis reference-mapping method for the comparisons with the lowest **D** and the highest **E** overall accuracy (B cell-CD14 monocyte). The bar plot above the UMAP corresponds to the cell type labels against which the query cell type, ablated in the reference, was classified. The confidence scores represent the proportion of K neighbours from the winning class ($K=10$). Ellipses circumscribe the position of the ablated cell type.

Extended Data Figure 8 Accuracy performance of Coralysis reference-mapping method for a query-reference scenario of varied strength of the batch effect. **A** Joint PCA of reference and query PBMC datasets. Reference and query consisted of resting and interferon stimulated PBMCs. Shapes represent reference-query identity and colours cell types. Distributions on top and left highlight cell types and dataset identity across PC1 and PC2, respectively. Dashed lines across PC2 dataset-identity distributions correspond to the cell type centroids across reference-query. **B** Cross-batch centroid (Euclidean) distance between reference-query cell types. Dissimilarity corresponds to the diagonal distances min-max scaled. Closeness corresponds to the Euclidean distances scaled to fit in the range [0-1] by subtracting from one the distance divided by the maximum distance. **C** Sankey plot showing the correspondence between ground-truth cell type labels and predictions in percentage. Query projected onto the reference UMAP highlighting the dataset identity **D**, ground-truth cell labels **E**, predictions and confidence scores **F** between the reference and query (top-bottom). The confidence scores represent the proportion of K neighbours from the winning class ($K=10$).